

Question raised by requestor

Which criteria of interpretation do different member states use in order to evaluate that housing calves meets the standards detailed in Council Directive 2008/119/EC?

Answer

EURCAW *Ruminants & Equines* refers to the following documents:

- Thematic Factsheet – Visual and tactile contact in individually housed calves; available online at https://www.eurcaw-ruminants-equines.eu/knowledge_base/structural-features-of-partitions-between-individually-housed-calves/
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7648848>
- Indicator Factsheet – Visual and tactile contact in individually housed calves; available online at https://www.eurcaw-ruminants-equines.eu/knowledge_base/definition-of-levels-of-restriction-of-visual-and-tactile-contact-in-pens-for-individually-housing-calves/
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7648880>

